

ATTITUDE TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL STATISTICS AMONG THE B.ED. TEACHER-TRAINEES

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Abstract

The study is designed for finding the attitude of B. Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream towards Educational Statistics. For the present study the investigator randomly selected the 100 B.Ed. teacher-trainees from College of Education, Nashik. Out of this 50 teacher-trainees are of Arts and 50 are of Science Stream. In it 25 male and 25 female teacher-trainees of Arts stream, and 25 male and 25 female teacher-trainees of Science stream. Appropriate analysis was carried out on the collected data. It was found that there is a significant difference in the Mean scores of attitude towards Educational Statistics of male and female teacher-trainees of Arts stream. But there is no significant difference in the mean scores of attitude towards Educational Statistics of male and female teacher-trainees of Science stream, male teacher-trainees of Arts and Science stream, female teacher-trainees of Arts and Science stream and combined teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Introduction

Educational Statistics is a compulsory course for the B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Pune University. Attitude towards Educational Statistics of teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream affects the actions related to this course. Positive attitude towards Educational Statistics makes easier to understand the concepts of Educational Statistics and solving the different types of problems of Educational Statistics, and also creates the interest and favourable attitudes among the teacher-trainees.. The present study is mainly designed for finding the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the male and female B.Ed. Teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Statement of the Problem

A Study of the Attitudes of Male and Female B.Ed. Teacher-trainees towards Educational Statistics in relation to Arts and Science Stream

Operational Definitions of Terms

Attitude:

Predisposition to perceive, feel or behave towards specific objects or certain people in a particular manner. Attitudes are thought to be derived from experience rather than innate characteristics, which suggest that they can be modified.

Male B.Ed. teacher-trainees:

Boy's students who are studying in Faculty of Education, to get degree of Bachelor of Education.

Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees:

Girl's students studying in faculty of Education, to get degree of Bachelor of Education.

Educational Statistics:

Educational Statistics is a compulsory Course for the students studying in Faculty of Education, to get degree of Bachelor of Education from University of Pune.

Arts Stream:

The teacher-trainees who acquired a degree Bachelor of Arts, and admitted to B. Ed. Course.

Science Stream:

The teacher-trainees who acquired a degree Bachelor of Science, and admitted to B.Ed.Course.

Objectives of the Study

Following are the objectives of the study

- 1) To study the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
- 2) To study the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Female B.Ed.

- teacher- trainees.
- 3) To compare the attitude towards Educational Statistics of Male and Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
 - 4) To study the attitude towards Educational Statistics of B.Ed.teacher-trainees of Arts Stream.
 - 5) To study the attitude towards Educational Statistics of B.Ed.teacher-trainees of Science Stream.
 - 6) To compare the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Hypotheses

- 1) There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male and Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of the Arts Stream.
- 2) There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male and Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of the Science Stream.
- 3) There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.
- 4) There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.
- 5) There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male and Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Research Methodology

In order to achieve the objectives of the study and the resources available the Survey Method was used.

Sample of the Study

The Sample of the study includes 100 B.Ed. teacher-trainees studying in the College of Education, Nashik.Out of which 25 Male and 25 Female teacher-trainees

of Arts Stream, and 25 Male and 25 Female teacher-trainees of Science Stream.

Tools used for Study

Tool used for the study is Standardized Scale prepared by Investigator, entitled-“The Educational Statistics Attitude Scale” having reliability 0.7582 and validity 0.8707. From these two coefficients, it is concluded that the scale is highly valid and reliable. The Scale consists of 24 statements, of which 12 are positive and 12 are negative.

Procedure of the Study

The Educational Statistics Attitude Scale was administered on 100 B.Ed. teacher-trainees, in it there was a 50 teacher-trainees of Arts Stream, and 50 teacher-trainees of Science Stream.i.e.25 Male and 25 Female teacher-trainees of Arts stream, and 25 Male and 25 Female teacher-trainees of Science stream.

Afterwards the responses were scored, tabulated and analyzed by using Statistical techniques.

Statistical techniques used

- 1) Mean
- 2) Standard Deviation (S.D.)
- 3) t-value

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis – 1 : There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male and Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Art Stream.

Table-1: Difference in attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male and Female B.Ed teacher-trainees of Arts Stream.

Arts stream	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Level of Significance
Male	25	77.4	7.31	2.47	0.05
Female	25	72.38	7.02		Significant

The ideal t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.02 and the calculated t-value is 2.47. The calculated t-value is greater than the ideal t-value. Therefore the hypothesis-1 is rejected.

Therefore it was inferred that there is a significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts Stream.

Hypothesis-2: There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male and Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Science Stream.

Table-2: Difference in attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male and Female B.Ed teacher-trainees of Science Stream.

Science Stream	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Level of Significance
Male	25	76.12	5.59	0.86	0.05
Female	25	74.76	5.55		Not Significant

The ideal t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.02 and the calculated t-value is 0.86. The calculated t-value is less than the ideal t-value, hence it is not significant. Therefore the hypothesis-2 is accepted.

It was inferred that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Science stream.

Hypothesis-3: There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Table-3: Difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Male B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science stream.

Stream	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Level of Significance
Arts-Male	25	77.4	7.31	0.69	0.05
Science-Male	25	76.12	5.59		Not Significant

The ideal t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.02 and the calculated t-value is 0.69. The calculated t-value is less than the ideal t-value, hence it is not significant.

The hypothesis-3 is accepted because the calculated t-value is less than the ideal t-value.

Therefore it was inferred that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of male B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Hypothesis-4: There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Table-4: Difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the Female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science stream.

Stream	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Level of Significance
Arts- Female	25	72.38	7.02	1.32	0.05
Science-Female	25	74.76	5.59		Not Significant

The ideal t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.02 and the calculated t-value is 1.32. The calculated t-value is less than the ideal t-value, hence it is not significant. Therefore the hypothesis-4 is accepted.

It was inferred that there is significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Hypothesis-5: There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Table-5: Difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science stream.

Stream	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Level of significance
Arts	50	73.94	8.18	1.03	0.05
Science	50	75.48	6.69		Not significant

The ideal t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 1.99 and the calculated t-value is 1.03. The ideal t-value is more than the calculated t-value, hence it is not significant. Consequently the Hypothesis-5 is accepted.

It was inferred that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science Stream.

Major Findings of the Study

1. There is significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts stream.
2. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Science stream.
3. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the male B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science stream.
4. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of female B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts stream.
5. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards Educational Statistics of the B.Ed. teacher-trainees of Arts and Science stream.

References

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